

**Brand Preference of Gearless Two-Wheelers in Palayamkottai
Tirunelveli District**

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ABSTRACT

Brand preference is the measure of brand loyalty in which a consumer will choose a particular brand in presence of competing brands, but will accept the substitute if that brand is not available. Brand preference is the selective demand for a company's brand rather than a product. The degree to which a consumer prefer one brand over the another. To analyse the brand preference it is necessary to study the consumers' buying behaviour and after purchase satisfaction.

Keywords: Brand Preference, Brand Loyalty, Two-Wheelers.

INTRODUCTION

The two wheeler industry in our country is constantly growing. It is really amazing how two wheeler markets have developed on in the last two decades, the Indian two wheeler industry has finally transformed to this level of achievement. As an insight of the fact that consumer brand preference towards two wheeler turn modernity. The result of liberalisation and globalisation surfaced way people in rural areas did not want to wait or the bus, automatically their preference turn towards two wheeler. Today effectual consumer brand preferences of two

wheelers are individual, in to mars, segment demand, reliability, Morden styling, economy and purchasing power.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To study the socio-economic conditions of the respondents
2. To review the history and development of transportation and two wheeler industry.
3. To study the profile of Hero, Honda, TVS , Bajaj and Yamaha companies
4. To analyse the buying behaviour of selected gearless two wheelers.
5. To offer suggestions based upon the findings of the study

Hypotheses: H₀1: There is no association between age and brand of the motor cycle

METHODOLOGY

Primary data

The primary data collected through questionnaire administered to a sample of 120 consumers selected form Palayamkottai. A questionnaires of 25 questions had been constructed and use in the survey. The scheduled questionnaire was framed.

Secondary data

Secondary data was collected using various journals, books, and research papers, newspaper, magazines, websites etc.,

Sampling Size: 120 number of respondents from Palayamkottai.

Statistical tool used: Percentage method, Garret Ranking Analysis Method, and Chi-Square Test.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- ❖ The study is conducted only in Palayamkottai.
- ❖ We have made analysis only with limited sample
- ❖ Our study aims at brand preference of gearless two wheeler.
- ❖ Term duration for conducting research is very limited due to lack of time extensive research is not conducted.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

**TABLE 1.1
BRAND OF THE VEHICLE**

S.No.	Brand of the vehicle	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Honda	40	33.33
2.	Hero	35	29.17
3.	TVS	20	16.67
4.	Yamaha	15	12.5
5.	Bajaj	10	8.33
	Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

We can infer from the above table 1.1 out of 120 respondents, 33.33 percent of the respondents are using Honda brand of two wheelers, 29.17 percent of the respondents are using Hero brand of two wheelers, 16.67 percent of the respondents are using TVS brand of two wheelers, 12.5 percent of the respondents are using Yamaha brand of two wheelers, and 8.33 percent of the respondents are using Bajaj brand of two wheelers.

Therefore 40 percent of the respondents are using Honda brand of two wheelers.

**TABLE 1.2
SATISFACTION LEVEL ON INFLUENCING FACTORS**

Sl. No.	Particulars	HS	S	M	DS	HDS	TOTAL
1	Brand image	32 (26.7)	36 (30)	14 (11.7)	24 (20)	14 (11.7)	120 (100)
2	Fuel economy	10 (8.4)	24 (20)	46 (38.3)	36 (30)	4 (3.3)	120 (100)
3	Maintenance cost	6 (5)	34 (28.3)	38 (31.7)	28 (23.3)	14 (11.7)	120 (100)

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4	Pick-up	20 (16.7)	30 (25)	34 (28.3)	26 (21.6)	10 (8.4)	120 (100)
5	Elegant appeal	28 (23.3)	26 (21.7)	24 (20)	22 (18)	20 (17)	120 (100)
6	Availability of vehicle	24 (20)	38 (31.7)	34 (28.3)	12 (10)	12 (10)	120 (100)
7	Resale value	8 (6.6)	18 (15)	36 (30)	32 (26.7)	26 (21.7)	120 (100)
8	Finance facility	16 (13.3)	38 (31.7)	24 (20)	30 (25)	12 (10)	120 (100)
9	After sale service	14 (11.7)	48 (40)	24 (20)	30 (25)	4 (3.3)	120 (100)

Weighted Average = Total / No. of Respondents

TABLE 1.3
REASON FOR CHOOSING THE GEARLESS VEHICLES

S.No	Reason for Choosing	Mean Score	Rank
1	Attractive look	71.05	I
2	Better performance	63.08	II
3	Efficient dealers service	51.02	III
4	Moderate price	34.64	IV
5	Comfort	28.24	V
6	Image	23.84	VI

On the basis of garret ranking, the reason for choosing the gearless vehicles from Attractive look scored rank I, Better performance scored rank II, Efficient dealer's service scored rank III, Moderate price scored rank IV, comfort scored rank V, and image scored rank VI.

TABLE 1.4

Hypothesis 2

There is no association between age and brand of the motor cycle.

S.no	Age	Brand					Total
		Hero	Honda	TVS	Bajaj	Yamaha	
1	Below 25	15	10	12	2	1	40
2	26-35	4	4	4	2	6	20
3	36-45	4	12	6	4	4	30
4	Above45	7	10	2	2	9	30
	Total	30	36	24	10	20	120

S.no	Age	Brand					Total
		Hero	Honda	TVS	Bajaj	Yamaha	
1	Below 25	10	8	12	3	7	40
2	26-35	5	4	6	2	3	20

3	36-45	7	6	9	3	5	30
4	Above45	8	6	9	2	5	30
	Total	30	36	24	10	20	120

O	E	O-E	$(O-E)^2$	$(O-E)^2/E$
15	10	5	25	2.5
10	12	-2	4	0.33
12	8	4	16	2
2	3	-1	1	0.33
1	7	-6	36	5.14
4	5	-1	1	0.2
4	4	0	0	0
4	6	-2	4	0.67
2	2	0	0	0
6	3	3	9	3
4	7	-3	9	1.29
6	6	0	0	0
12	9	3	9	1
4	3	1	1	0.33
4	5	-1	1	0.2
7	8	1	1	0.125
2	6	-4	16	2.67
10	9	1	1	0.11
2	2	0	0	0
9	5	4	16	3.2
				23.095

Calculated value is 23.095

Table value is 7.815

(@ 5% df)

The calculated value is more than table value, the hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is an association between age and brand of the motor cycle.

Findings

- The gearless two wheelers bikemore usingfemale gender.
- Most of the respondents are in the age group of Below 25 years of age.
- The majority of the respondents have their income between Rs.20, 001 – Rs.30, 000.
- Most of the consumer is preferred Honda company Bikes.

Suggestions

- Hero motors should provide good warranty and after sale service.
- Honda should focus on improving quality of female two-wheelers.
- TVS should concentrate in designing of male two-wheelers.
- Bajaj should concentrate in quality of two-wheelers.
- Yamaha should adopt more advertising strategies for male category.

Conclusion

The study helped to me to have a good insight about the brand preference of gearless two-wheelers among consumers. It is found from the study that the prime factor influencing the consumers' preference of gearless two-wheelers is quality and design. So that the selected companies should take necessary effective steps to improve their activities based on the suggestions.

REFERENCE

Journals

- MuthuKarthic, M., "Customer's Satisfaction Towards Hero Honda Motor Cycle in Madurai city", Unpublished M.Phil. dissertation submitted to Madurai Kamaraj University, August 2006.
- Thomas P. Poghishyo, "Brand selection – A Study of Consumer Preference for Two Wheeler (with special reference to Madurai City)", Unpublished Thesis 1991.

Books

- H.P. Gupta and Raghbir Sing (1989), "Consumers Brand Choice Behaviour for Television", Indian Journal of Marketing, Vol.19 No.6, 7, p.17.
- C.R. Kothari (2000), "Research Methodology - Methods and Techniques", ViswaPrakasan, New Delhi.

Websites

- www.automobileindia.com
- www.heromotorcorp.com
- www.hondaactiva.com
- www.wikipedia.com